

Optimisation model for a closed-loop industrial water-energy system within a ceramic industry plant

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Abstract

The water-energy nexus, dealing with all potential interdependencies between water and energy resources, may be promoted throughout various practices, with a part of these still not being implemented or even conceptualized. In the context of end-use sectors, several types of water systems are installed. These water systems necessarily consume energy (either electricity or fuels), and in the case of open loop systems these also consume considerable quantities of water. An approach implemented for the reduction of both freshwater and hot/ cold utilities in a water system is designated as Combined Water and Energy Integration. In this work, it is presented the development of a non-linear programming (NLP) model for the minimization of water and energy in a water recirculation and treatment system installed in a ceramic plant. The model is part of the ThermWatt computational tool and is built with the Python language (using the GEKKO package). An economic and environmental viability was performed for the Engineering project encompassing the water recirculation and treatment system. A payback time of 2 years and 10 months and an emissions reduction of 1.76 kton CO_{2,eq}/year have been estimated, demonstrating a high viability of the proposed installation in comparison to a benchmark of 2 – 3 years reasonable payback period and a maximum value of 0.722 kton CO_{2,eq}/year reduction for similar plants.

1. Introduction

The improvement of water and energy efficiency is an important concern of several end-use sectors to not only increase the economic value of businesses but also to comply with the specific objectives of the most recent sustainability policies [1]. In the context of process industry plants, several categories of water systems are installed for different operational ends [2].

A generic water system constituted by a set of water-using processes (to which water streams are transported to remove a set of contaminants) may be analysed through the conceptualization of advanced configurations considering the implementation of water treatment units to remove a part of the contaminants from the discharge water streams from the aforementioned processes, in addition to several specific water recirculation points [3]. A methodology implemented for the purpose of minimizing the input of freshwater and hot/ cold utilities in these systems ,through the promotion of the circular economy and closed-loop characters associated to water recirculation, is designated as Combined Water and Energy Integration [4]. This methodology is commonly implemented through the optimisation of models linear, non-linear models for single objective or multi-objective goals. [5].

This work presents the development and further use of a non-linear programming (NLP) model for the purpose of assessing the optimal point of the operation of a water treatment and recirculation systems installed in a ceramic plant , in which operational costs associated to water and hot/ cold utilities usage are minimised. The developed optimisation model has been created on the Python language (using the GEKKO package), being part of the customised ThermWatt computational tool (intellectual property of ISQ – Instituto de Soldadura e Qualidade).

2. Experimental

The GEKKO package within Python 3.11 version software was used for the development of the proposed non-linear programming (NLP) model. The internal IPOPT software and MUMPS solver of GEKKO package were used for the running of the model. The NLP methodology is used for the present case-study due to the formulation of the mass balance, enthalpy balance and heat transfer equations that define the system, although the objective-function is constituted by linear terms only. Such modelling methodology has already been used for a single-contaminant water system problem in previous works by the authors,

being tested for this work with a multi-contaminant problem , considering three salt contaminants. In Figure 1, the water system baseline case configuration and stream characterization are presented. In Figure 2, the flowsheet for the superstructure for the refurbished water system is presented. The superstructure configuration represents only a part of an overall project, which not only encompasses the approached water system but also a set of four combustion-based processes, with the waste heat streams from two of these (Kilns 1 and 2) being recirculated to the water system. The refurbished water system superstructure considers (in addition to the several points of water recirculation) the installation of a multi-effect distillation (MED) for the removal of salt contaminants and an electrolysis unit to produce hydrogen from the discharge water stream from the whole system.

The objective-function based on energy and water-related unitary costs that multiply to the respective energy and water inputs, is presented in equation (1). The decision variables and equality constraints characterizing the optimisation model have been formulated in the basis of the same set of variables and equations defined in a previous publication of the authors [1].

Figure 1. Baseline case flowsheet

Figure 2. Superstructure flowsheet (considering an identification of water streams to be furtherly used to characterized the final optimisation results)

$$\min \left(1.8499 (\text{€}/\text{m}^3) \cdot \frac{1}{999} (\text{m}^3/\text{kg}) \cdot \dot{M}_{\text{FW}} (\text{kg}/\text{h}) + 23.66 (\text{€}/\text{GJ}) \cdot q_{\text{HotUt}} (\text{GJ}/\text{h}) + 0.1459 (\text{€}/\text{kWh}) \cdot \frac{1}{0.95} \cdot \frac{1}{3600} (\text{kWh}/\text{GJ}) \cdot q_{\text{ColdUt}} (\text{GJ}/\text{h}) \right) (\text{€}/\text{h}) \quad (1)$$

In relation to the objective-function:

- The unitary value of 23.66 €/GJ was considered for natural gas used as hot utility;
- The unitary value of 0.1459 €/kWh was considered for cold utility;
- The unitary price of 1.8499 €/ m³ was considered for freshwater.

3. Results and Discussion

The final optimisation results was attained through the following procedure:

- Firstly, the developed optimisation model was run to obtain primary results;
- In a next phase, a sensitivity analysis procedure was implemented, in which several parameters of the model (mainly, assumed constants and lower and upper limits of determinate variables) were tested. Such procedure (based on a one-at-a-time (OAT) method) was mainly set to improve the robustness of the developed model;
- The performance of the sensitivity analysis procedure allowed a final configuration scenario for the water system, which is the one used for the whole post-processing assessment.

The results for the performed sensitivity analysis are presented in the sequence of Tables I and II. In Table III, the designations corresponding to the variables numbers (1 and 2) in the mentioned tables are presented.

Table I. Sensitivity analysis results (Part 1)

Variables	Adjustment	Freshwater (m ³ /h)	Hot utility (MJ/h)	Cold utility (MJ/h)	Discharge water (m ³ /h)	Hot air (Kiln 1) (ton/h)	Hot air (Kiln 2) (ton/h)	Total operational costs (€/h)
1					21.62			
2								
16.53	1	0.527				15.30	6.33	0.976
0.00	2	0.538				2.55		0.996
1					0.00			
2								
16.53	3	0.528				21.62	5.86	0.976
0.00	4	0.552	78.14	1.74		21.62		2.944
Salt 1 (ppm)					2000.00			
1					21.62			
2								
16.53	5	0.525		13.00		7.42	9.02	1.526
0.00	6	0.529				2.68		0.978
Salt 1 (ppm)					2000.00			
1					0.00			
2								
16.53	7	0.537				21.62	1.65	0.993
0.00	8	0.536	6.21			21.62		1.138
Salt 2 (ppm)					2000.00			
1					21.62			
2								
16.53	9	0.528				15.81	3.96	0.977
0.00	10	0.529				6.14		0.978
Salt 2 (ppm)					2000.00			
1					0.00			
2								
16.53	11	0.529				21.62	4.17	0.978
0.00	12	0.576	38.28	0.40		21.62		1.989
Salt 3 (ppm)					2000.00			
1					21.62			
2								
16.53	13	1.033		63.74	0.760	18.30		4.630
0.00	14	0.528				2.47		0.978
Salt 3 (ppm)					2000.00			
1					0.00			
2								
16.53	15	0.527				21.62	5.91	0.976
0.00	16	1.033		42.75	0.696	21.62		3.730

Table II. Sensitivity analysis results (Part 2)

Variables	Adjustment	Freshwater (m ³ /h)	Hot utility (MJ/h)	Cold utility (MJ/h)	Discharge water (m ³ /h)	Hot air (Kiln 1) (ton/h)	Hot air (Kiln 2) (ton/h)	Total operational costs (€/h)
1					16.53			
2								

21.62	17	0.527			15.30	6.33	0.976
0.00	18	0.528				3.67	0.976
1	2				0.00		
21.62	19	1.033		1.53	0.562	21.56	16.53
0.00	20	0.531					16.53
Salt 1 (ppm)					2000.00		
1	2				16.53		
21.62	21	0.525		13.00		7.42	9.02
0.00	22	0.538	26.22				1.55
Salt 1 (ppm)					2000.00		
1	2				0.00		
21.62	23	0.537				21.50	16.53
0.00	24	0.528					16.53
Salt 2 (ppm)					2000.00		
1	2				16.53		
21.62	25	0.717	18.04	5.74		11.98	0.03
0.00	26	0.528					1.82
Salt 2 (ppm)					2000.00		
1	2				0.00		
21.62	27	0.530				15.45	16.53
0.00	28	0.546					16.53
Salt 3 (ppm)					2000.00		
1	2				16.53		
21.62	29	1.033		63.74	0.760	18.30	
0.00	30	0.692	186.45	3.35			0.43
Salt 3 (ppm)					2000.00		
1	2				0.00		
21.62	31	0.529				13.40	16.53
0.00	32	1.033		57.90	0.731	0.00	16.53

Table III. Designations for the parameters for Sensitivity Analysis

Designation	Part 1	Part 2
1	Non-recirculated hot air from Kiln 1 (ton/h)	Non-recirculated hot air from Kiln 2 (ton/h)
2	Recirculated hot air from Kiln 2 (ton/h)	Recirculated hot air from Kiln 1 (ton/h)

Taking into account the aforementioned, it is possible to conclude that considerable improvements in terms of robustness may be performed in respect to the initial optimisation model. It is possible to obtain the following primary findings:

- In the majority of the performed adjustments, only small variations are verified in the analysed indicators, with relatively low freshwater consumption and hot and cold utility consumption (which reach null levels in a considerable number of the total adjustments);
- Nonetheless, in the adjustments associated to highest constraints in terms of supplied hot air (this is, in which the upper bound corresponding to the hot air allocated from one of the kilns to the water system is set as null or the upper bound for the hot air that is non-recirculated to the water system is null), it is verified either a considerably higher freshwater consumption or a higher level of consumption of either hot utility or cold utility, which corresponds to an increase in the total operational costs (which are the cases of adjustments 4, 8, 12 and 19);
- In respect to the corresponding adjustments associated to the variation of the upper bounds of concentrations of each one of the salts, it is possible to verify the inexistence of an agreement between the results throughout the comparison of several corresponding adjustments (a set of corresponding adjustments have associated lower operational costs for higher salt concentration and other sets have associated higher operational costs). As such, the consideration of the variation of the referred parameter shall be interpreted only for purposes of revise optimisation results rather than for assessment of model robustness;
- For a set of performed adjustments, it is possible to obtain a similar level of benefits in relation to the initial optimization results for reduced levels of supplied hot air from each one of the kilns (as may be verified for adjustments 2, 6, 10, 14 and 18). Such may be attributed to a tendency to maintain similar levels of water recirculation within the water system in between scenarios, and as such similar levels of water and energy use, as the defined objective for the optimisation problem is the reduction of water

and energy use-related costs. In this prospect, it may be considered that the performed adjustments on the upper bounds of each one of the allocated hot air-related variables increase the robustness of the developed model in relation to the proposed objective (achieve a compromise between the reduction of total operational costs and the allocation of hot air).

Based on the previous achievements, it may be considered that although the initial optimisation model for the water system is robust in respect to the minimization of total operational costs (which is formulated as the objective-function), further adjustments may be performed to increase the overall robustness of the model in relation the objectives set as secondary (in this case, the reduction of the quantity of allocated hot air for the same level of obtained benefits). In this case, such augment of robustness related to this secondary objective is pertinent due to the fact the model has been developed only for a part of the overall conceptualized system (in this case only the water system, and not the overall WEIS). The stream allocation configuration obtained associated to the adopted configuration following sensitivity analysis (corresponding to adjustment 10) is presented in Figure 3.

WC1	WC2	WC3
25.43 kg/h	58.62 kg/h	10.87 kg/h
In: 70.27 °C Out: 70.27 °C	In: 65.50 °C Out: 65.50 °C	In: 84.35 °C Out: 84.35 °C
C1: 627.30 ppm C2: 586.40 ppm C3: 580.75 ppm	C1: 606.61 ppm C2: 606.61 ppm C3: 606.61 ppm	C1: 718.02 ppm C2: 659.00 ppm C3: 648.61 ppm
Air1	AirMED	AirOut
6141.24 kg/h 111.47 °C	3980.05 kg/h 111.47 °C	6141.24 kg/h 84.53 °C
AirHT1	AirHT2	
336.33 kg/h	1824.86 kg/h	
In Econ. 1: 111.47 °C Out Heater 1: 91.73 °C	In Econ. 1: 111.47 °C Out Heater 1: 49.48 °C	

Figure 3. Flowsheet of the optimised configuration

Table IV. Assessment of savings and economic and environmental viability

Utility/ Cost Parcel	Baseline	Optimised	
Water System			
Freshwater Flow Rate (m³/h)	0.861	0.529	
Hot Utility Consumption (GJ/h)			
Heater 1	0.125		
Heater 2	0.180		
Heater 3	0.033		
Cold Utility Consumption (GJ/h)			
Cooler 1	0.085		
Cooler 2	0.133		
Cooler 3	0.017		
Overall			
Total Operational Cost (€/h)	19.10	0.978	
Total Operational Cost (k€/year)	149.47	7.65	
Final Assessment (Overall project considering water-using and combustion-based processes)			
Investment Cost (k€)	Savings (k€/year)	Payback Time (Years)	CO_{2,eq} Reduction (kton CO_{2,eq}/year)
1802.81	637.91	2.83	1.76

The post-processing results demonstrate that the conceptualized project is viable in an economic and environmental perspective, in comparison to a benchmark of 2 – 3 years reasonable payback period and a maximum value of 0.722 kton CO_{2,eq}/year reduction. A significant improvement of water and energy use is also possible to be achieved for the approached water system and the overall plant, having been attained null levels of hot and cold utility consumption, null water discharge and a high freshwater input reduction.

4. Conclusions

This work presents an optimisation model developed for the purpose of minimizing the freshwater and hot/cold utility inputs on a water system, using the Combined Water and Energy Integration methodology. The development of the model subsisted on the application of the non-linear programming (NLP) method. The overall modelling methodology that has been already used for single-contaminant problems proved to be successful in the context of a multi-contaminant problem. The optimal configuration for the water system (encompassing a multi-effect distillation unit and several water recirculation points) serves as a basis for a potential Engineering project, which has been assessed through the determination of the economic and environmental viability. With the estimated payback period and absolute CO_{2,eq} emissions reduction levels being comparable to industrial benchmarks, the Engineering project reveals to be highly viable.

5. References

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